

CHARACTERISTICS OF CARBON-POLYCARBONATE INTERFACIAL SHEAR BONDING: A COARSE- GRAINED MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY

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BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

- Typical composite material:
 - A stiff phase(e.g., carbon)
 - A tough and flexible phase(e.g., polymers)

(Maiti, et al. 2022)

- Interface – where these phases connect – play the critical role in determining the mechanical performance of the material.

(Jain, et al. 2021)

(Gogoi, et al. 2023)

- Failure often initiates at the interface
- Bonding at the interface largely controls strength
- Molecular dynamics studies can provide insights into how interfacial bonding governs sliding, delamination and failure

STATE OF THE ART AND RESEARCH GAPS

State of the Art

	Tensile Failure Behavior (Molecular Scale)	Shear Failure (Molecular Scale)	Effect of Molecular Dispersity	Interface Roughness
Polycarbonate(PC) Polymer	(Kubo et al.2023)	(Yang et al.2021)	(Kubo et al.2023)	-
Other Composites (e.g., Cu-PE Composite, Cu-Epoxy Composite)	(Meng et al.2018) (Hue et al. 2025)	(Song et al.2022) (Jin et al. 2025)	(Wu et al.2020)	(Meng et al.2018) (Jin et al. 2025)

Research Gaps

- Interfacial shear behavior of carbon-polycarbonate-carbon(DLC–CGPC–DLC) sandwich structures.
- How carbon surface roughness affects mechanical performance under shear.
- How polycarbonate molecular dispersity influences composite shear strength.

Polymer: Coarse-grained Polycarbonate(CGPC)

- Force Field (morse): describes the energy of interaction between two particles

Single Polycarbonate Monomer

- Bonding(within single chain):

$$E_{intra} = \sum_{b:bond} \sum_{l=2}^4 K_l^b (b - b_0)^l + \sum_{\theta:angle} \sum_{m=2}^4 K_m^a (\theta - \theta_0)^m$$

- b: bond length
- θ : bond angle
- K: force constant

- Non-Bond(among chains):

$$E_{inter} = \sum_{i<j} D_0 \{ \exp[-2\beta(R_{ij} - R_0)] - 2\exp[-\beta(R_{ij} - R_0)] \}$$

- R: distance
- D_0 : Depth of the potential well
- i, j: 2 particles in different chains

- Modeling Process

Initial Simulation Cell

1 atm and 300 K

Final Simulation Cell

Carbon: Diamond-liked Carbon

- Force Field (Tersoff)

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} V_{ij}$$

- V include both two-body and three-body interactions

- Modeling Process

Diamond-like Carbon(DLC)

Diamond Carbon (Crystalline): Extremely hard

1. Heating
2. Fast Cooling

Diamond-liked Carbon (Amorphous): not as hard as diamond structure

METHOD

Composite Model

- Force Field (12/6 Lennard-Jones (LJ)) between PC and C

$$E = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 \right], \quad r < r_c$$

σ : distance where the potential crosses 0.
 ϵ : depth of the potential well(energy scale).

- Mixing Rules: for generating cross interaction LJ parameters

- Good-Hope Mixing Rule:

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{ii}\epsilon_{jj}}, \quad \sigma_{ij} = \sqrt{\sigma_{ii}\sigma_{jj}}$$

- Lorentz-Berthelot Mixing Rule:

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{ii}\epsilon_{jj}}, \quad \sigma_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{ii} + \sigma_{jj}}{2}$$

- Waldman-Hagler Mixing Rule:

$$\epsilon_{ij} = 2\sqrt{\epsilon_{ii}\epsilon_{jj}} \left(\frac{\sigma_{ii}^3\sigma_{jj}^3}{\sigma_{ii}^6 + \sigma_{jj}^6} \right), \quad \sigma_{ij} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{ii}^6 + \sigma_{jj}^6}{2}}$$

i and j: 2 different particle types

DLC-CGPC-DLC Model

Mixing Rules Investigation: uniaxial tensile test

	Good-Hope(GH)	Lorentz-berthelot(LB)	Waldman-Hagler(WH)
Features	Symmetric; simple to apply	General default	Avoids overly strong attraction LB or GH can predict
Limitations	May underestimate σ	Can be less accurate for heterogeneous systems	Complex; less common in polymer simulations

(Mirskaya, et al. 1973)

- Result:
 - WH: interfacial connection too weak
 - GH & LB: similar performance

Final Pick: Lorentz-Berthelot(LB) Mixing Rule

Good-Hope (GH)

Lorentz-Berthelot (LB)

Waldman-Hagler (WH)

Roughness

DLC Roughness Edition:

1. Generate flat carbon layers
2. Set roughness height(H) and roughness width(W)
3. Create sine wave
 - Use H as half amplitude
 - Use W as period
4. Align sine curve with carbon surface
5. Cut carbon atoms below the curve

Molecular Dispersity (PDI) of PC

Polydispersity Index(PDI) is a measure of how uniform polymer chain length are in the Model

$$PDI = \frac{M_w}{M_n}$$

M_w : weight-average molecular weight

M_n : number-average molecular weight

- PDI=1: monodisperse, all chains are the same length
- PDI>1: polydisperse, chain length vary

Case 1(PDI=1.56):

224 monomer chain * 16

+

32 monomer chain * 16

Case 2(PDI=1):

128 monomer chain * 32

Case 1 vs. Case 2

- Total # of chain: 32
- Total # of monomer: 4096

METHOD: SIMULATION

Shear Test Setting

Lx (Å)	120
Ly (Å)	120
Lz (Å)	113 ~ 122
Number of PC Particles	16384
Number of Carbon Atoms	56000~94000
Simulation Timestep (fs)	1

RESULT

Video: $W=20$, $H=9$, $PDI=1$

RESULT

Video: $W = 60$, $H=9$, $PDI=1$

RESULT

Effect of Roughness Width(W)

- As roughness width(W) increases, interfacial interlocking weakens.
 - Broader spacing of surface features → reduce local curvature → decrease the number of effective contact points for resistance

RESULT

Effect of Roughness Height(H)

- As roughness height(H) decreases, interfacial interlocking weakens.
 - Shallower surface asperities → less geometric constraint → easier slipping

RESULT

Effect of CGPC Molecular Dispersity(PDI)

- The monodisperse system (PDI = 1) exhibits a higher peak shear stress than the polydisperse system (PDI = 1.56).
 - PDI = 1
 - Uniform chain length → more consistent packing and entanglement → stronger interlocking

➤ Method

- Modeling Process of Carbon-Polycarbonate-Carbon(DLC-CGPC-DLC) System
 - Polymer (CGPC) + Carbon (DLC) → DLC-CGPC-DLC Model
 - Mixing Rules: Good-Hope(GH) vs. Lorentz-Berthelot(LB) vs. Waldman-Hagler(WH)
 - Best Choice: Lorentz-Berthelot(LB)
- Shear Tests: Roughness and PDI setting

➤ Results

- As roughness width(W) increases, interfacial interlocking weakens due to broader spacing of surface features.
- As roughness height(H) decreases, interfacial interlocking weakens due to shallower surface asperities.
- The monodisperse system ($PDI = 1$) exhibits a higher peak shear stress than the polydisperse system ($PDI = 1.56$), because uniform chains share load more effectively

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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Thank you for your interest!

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